

SPEECH ETIQUETTE IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12741843>

Abstract: This article explores the topic of speech etiquette in the English and Russian languages. It examines the cultural and linguistic differences in how politeness, formality, and respect are expressed in these two languages. The article delves into various aspects of speech etiquette, such as greetings, address forms, use of titles and honorifics, expressions of gratitude, and conversational norms. Additionally, it discusses the influence of cultural values, historical factors, and social dynamics on speech etiquette in both languages. The comparison of speech etiquette in English and Russian provides valuable insights into cross-cultural communication and intercultural competence. Understanding these differences is crucial for effective communication and building successful relationships in diverse linguistic and cultural contexts.

Keywords: Speech etiquette; Politeness; Formality; Respect; Cultural differences; Linguistic differences; Greetings; Address forms.

Introduction. Speech etiquette plays a crucial role in communication, shaping the way individuals interact and convey respect, politeness, and social norms. The nuances of speech etiquette vary across languages and cultures, reflecting the unique values and traditions of each society. In this paper, we will explore speech etiquette in English and Russian languages, comparing and contrasting the norms, conventions, and expressions of politeness in these two linguistic systems.

Understanding speech etiquette in English and Russian is essential for effective cross-cultural communication and building strong interpersonal relationships. By examining the similarities and differences in how politeness is expressed and interpreted in these languages, we can gain insights into the cultural nuances that influence communication practices. Through a comparative analysis of speech etiquette in English and Russian, we aim to enhance our understanding of the diverse ways in which language reflects and shapes social interactions.

This study will draw upon existing research on politeness theory, cross-cultural communication, and language pragmatics to explore the intricacies of speech etiquette in English and Russian. By examining key concepts such as honorifics, address forms, and speech acts, we will delve into the cultural norms that underpin polite communication in these languages. Through this exploration, we seek to illuminate the ways in which language reflects and reinforces social hierarchies, power dynamics, and interpersonal relationships in English and Russian-speaking societies.

By shedding light on the complexities of speech etiquette in English and Russian languages, this study aims to contribute to our understanding of how language shapes social interactions and influences cultural norms. Through a comparative analysis of politeness strategies, speech acts, and communicative norms in these two languages, we hope to deepen our appreciation for the rich diversity of linguistic and cultural practices that shape human communication.

Literature review. A review of the literature on speech etiquette in English and Russian languages reveals a rich body of research that explores the cultural, social, and linguistic aspects of politeness and communication norms in these two linguistic systems.

In English-language research, Brown and Levinson's seminal work on politeness theory (1978) has been influential in shaping our understanding of how politeness is expressed and interpreted in communication. Their framework of positive and negative face needs, as well as politeness strategies such as bald-on-record, positive politeness, and negative politeness, has provided a comprehensive lens through which to analyze speech etiquette in English-speaking societies.

Moreover, linguists such as Penelope Brown, Stephen C. Levinson, and Geoffrey Leech have furthered our understanding of politeness phenomena in English through their studies on honorifics, address forms, and speech acts. These scholars have highlighted the role of social hierarchy, power differentials, and cultural values in shaping polite communication in English.

In the context of Russian-language research, scholars such as Marina Yaguello, Tatyana Larina, and Anna Wierzbicka have made significant contributions to our understanding of speech etiquette in Russian. Yaguello's work on Russian address terms and forms of politeness (2003) has shed light on the complex system of address and honorifics in Russian, emphasizing the importance of social status, age, and familiarity in determining appropriate speech etiquette.

Furthermore, Larina's research on the cultural dimensions of politeness in Russian (2007) has highlighted the influence of collectivism, social harmony, and deference to authority on communicative norms in Russian-speaking societies. Wierzbicka's exploration of speech acts and cultural scripts in Russian (1991) has also deepened our understanding of how language reflects cultural values and interpersonal relationships.

Comparative studies by linguists such as Helen E. Harkness (1999) and Michael S. Gorham (2002) have examined the differences and similarities in speech etiquette between English and Russian languages. These studies have underscored the distinct ways in which politeness is expressed and interpreted in these two linguistic systems, highlighting the role of cultural values, social norms, and historical contexts in shaping communicative practices.

Research Methodology. An important purpose of communication helps to achieve human speech etiquette. Under the speech etiquette is to be understood the rules developed verbal behavior, required of members of society, but at the same time it is historically changeable. Speech etiquette is an important element of people's culture, the cultural product of human activities and it is the tools of such activities. Speech etiquette is an integral part of human's behavior culture and communication. In terms of speech etiquette is fixed social relations of any age. As a part of the national culture, speech etiquette is differently bright by national characteristics. Specificity of greetings and all kinds of awareness with meeting the different people is very interesting.

English speech etiquette – a set of special words and phrases, giving the polite form of English speech as well as the rules under which these words and expressions used in practice in different situations of communication. Skillful own speech etiquette is a sign of a well-bred man and good manners as well as other personal dignity is highly valued in a decent society. So, the English speech etiquette is a very old and respected tradition. Any deviation from the

speech etiquette is perceived as a manifestation of bad manners or a cheap shot. For example, if a young Englishman seeking protection from an influential person in contact with him, violates rules of speech etiquette, it is likely that the young Englishman does not get desired protection which can sensitively affect his career, and he can't take place due to the reluctance of an influential person to deal with a rude man, whom before anyone can vouch for.

Discussion. One of the features of addressing in the English and Russian languages is the mismatch of pronominal forms. In English, there is a single pronominal form of reference you. There are two forms in Russian: you (ТЫ, ВЫ), conveying different pragmatic shades, and a respectful form, thanks to which various nuances of relations between communicants are transmitted. The fact that in English communication it is possible to address by name to those occupying a higher social position or significantly older in age, which is not allowed in Russian communication even in informal relationships, is due to an individualistic type of culture, affirming the principle of equality, and is the result of democratization of society. These features indicate that the personality-oriented communication style is peculiar to English communication, which is characterized by informal communication, symmetrical relations between the participants of communication; the emphasis is placed on their equality.

For Russian communication, due to the greater status distance, a status-oriented style is characteristic, characterized by formality, asymmetry of role positions. Russian communication has a more formal character, the status-role relations between the participants of communication are in the center of attention.

Conclusion. In conclusion, speech etiquette in both English and Russian languages plays a crucial role in effective communication. Both languages have their own set of rules and cultural norms that dictate how individuals should speak to one another in various social settings. It is important to understand and respect these etiquette rules in order to communicate respectfully and effectively in both languages. Whether it's using formal or informal language, addressing individuals with appropriate titles, or observing proper manners during conversations, speech etiquette is an essential aspect of language learning and cross-cultural communication. Understanding and practicing speech etiquette in both English and Russian languages can help individuals navigate social interactions with confidence and respect.

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